

THE PROBLEM OF IMPROVING STUDENTS' COMPETENCES IN MATHEMATICS AND FORMING CREATIVE THINKING

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Abstract: This article aims to improve the basic competencies of students in mathematics, to bring mathematics education to a new level of quality at school. Information is given on the importance of forming critical and creative thinking in the teaching of mathematics and the role of mathematics in the logical thinking of the young generation.

Key words: mathematics, competence approach, formation of critical thinking, critical and creative thinking basic competencies, information and communication technologies.

INTRODUCTION

The importance of mathematics education is determined by its role in the development of science and technology, in the fields of production of information and communication technologies, and in everyday life. Along with the training of creative and creative personnel who meet the economic requirements, quality education should also be provided to those who use these achievements as consumers. Arousing interest in mathematics depends on the high level of the teaching method and the skillful construction of the educational work.

There are several goals and objectives of teaching mathematics in secondary education among them, understanding the importance of mathematics in human development and social development, socio-economic relations, teaching to successfully apply mathematical knowledge and skills in everyday life are the most important concepts.

Adoption of the decision PQ-4387 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 9, 2019 "On state support for the further development of mathematics education and sciences", the respect of mathematics teachers in society He once again mentioned the important role and responsibility they have. What are critical and creative thinking, and why are they important to study in relation to mathematics? If numbers are understood as referring to mathematics in everyday life. The term "critical numbering" is a multidisciplinary concept. One of the main tasks of learning mathematics is to acquire mathematical ability, the ability to solve simple and complex problems, and most importantly, to make the world made of numbers a better place through this skill.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The Mathematics Education Program in Australia provides teachers with an excellent opportunity to teach mathematics through critical and creative thinking. This is the main process of the educational program. The Australian Curriculum requires teachers to address four competencies: Problem Solving, Reasoning, Fluency and Comprehension. Problem solving and reasoning require critical and creative thinking. It is important to engage students in critical and creative thinking in every mathematics lesson. What for? By introducing critical and creative thinking in the lesson, we not only increase the effectiveness of the lesson, but also form the ability to understand the basic concept of mathematics and remember facts. Learning becomes more meaningful and purposeful for students. When and at what time can critical and creative thinking be promoted?

There are many tools and techniques that promote thinking. It's a good idea to start the process through several troubleshooting steps, but you can also use shorter or longer steps. Open-ended tasks are easy to complete, allowing all learners to succeed and think critically and creatively. Who should be involved in critical and creative thinking? Is this just for students? No! There are several reasons why teachers should be encouraged to think critically and creatively.

First, it means setting an example for students to think in this way.

Students tend to view math as black and white, right or wrong. They should learn to be creative and critical, to ask questions. They need to feel empowered to engage in research and teaching. They must transform from users of mathematics to producers. second, teachers as practicing mathematics teachers are critical and

they should think creatively. We are a continuous assessor, a critical thinker about a work plan that includes practical work and assessment, grouping students, a technology user, and finally a visionary for children to learn mathematics effectively. We must be a thoughtful practitioner.

In order to teach mathematics to students, the teacher should know these subjects well and be able to skillfully use teaching methods. At the same time, in-depth knowledge of pedagogy, psychology and other disciplines is necessary. The important goal of the training is to form the intellectual abilities of students, the skills of independent choice and decision-making, and to acquire the necessary knowledge.

Bringing mathematics education to a new quality level at school directly depends on the potential, professional skills and creativity of school teachers. It is known that improving the qualification of mathematics teachers, equipping them with modern educational methods and technologies is one of the serious issues facing mathematics education. In the organization of mathematics classes, it is necessary to pay more attention to practice than theory and to some extent abandon the approach based on providing students with ready-made educational materials.

All areas of mathematics are combined with the generality of science. It is known that real existence, spatial forms and quantitative relationships of the universe form the basis of mathematics. Various mathematical sciences deal with these spatial forms and special cases or special manifestations of quantitative relations. It can also be separated in its own way.

Competency approach to mathematical education implies the development and formation of practical skills that allow students to act effectively in situations encountered in their professional, personal and everyday life, as well as strengthening the practical directions of mathematical education.

Today, when new technical tools, including computers and other information technologies, are rapidly entering the teaching of mathematics, using the achievements of computer science in order to ensure interdisciplinary coherence is one of the urgent issues. The introduction of computer technologies in educational institutions opens a wide way to optimize the educational process.

Arousing interest in mathematics depends on the high level of the teaching method and how well the educational work is structured. In the lesson, it is necessary to make every student work actively and with pleasure, and to use the emergence and formation of his desire for knowledge as a starting point, to pay attention to deepening his interest in learning. This is especially important for teenagers, when it will be developed again, it is only necessary to determine their permanent interests and interest in this or that subject. At the same time, criticism of the attractive aspects of mathematics should be quick.

Teachers should have the skills to organize the process of lessons in the teaching of mathematics in non-traditional ways, to achieve the design of the educational process on the basis of a perfect model, to use these projects wisely. , deep assimilation, can be a guarantee of formation of practical skills and competencies.

CONCLUSION

By teaching students to be able to correctly express their thoughts about a mathematical law with symbols and, conversely, to be able to express the mathematical law expressed in the form of symbols in their native language, they will improve their mathematical and cultural skills. It is also possible to use modern information technology tools in teaching mathematics, explaining its

topics and organizing demonstrations. Critical and creative thinking is an irrefutable concept that we must always put at the forefront if we want the next generation to be ready for work and a constantly changing world. This understanding not only helps to prepare for the future, but also helps to produce highly skilled students, and makes mathematics useful and interesting.

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